

Some Structural Features of German Language Application Construction

Raximov Mirzali

Teacher of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages

Abstract. *This article discusses appositional constructions in the German language. It explores the identification of appositional relations based on lexical-semantic factors, as well as the relationship between the appositional element and the main expression. Additionally, the views of several linguists on the connectors used in appositional elements, their structural characteristics, and their application are also presented.*

Key words: *semantic factors of appositional relations, stylistic expressiveness, logical uniqueness of phenomena, through, whereas, because, so, that, u, но, да, und, aber connectors, emotional evaluation, expressive function, complex syntactic integrity, syntactic connection.*

The elements of the application not only replicate the features specific to the tasks they perform within the application structure but also continue to evolve by acquiring new characteristics, thereby expanding and enriching their functionality. The semantic factors of application connections lead to the semantic and structural independence between the application element and the main expression. The semantic separation of appositive elements from the first part of the main expression creates a basis for their placement in postposition (following position) in any appositive construction. Due to their logical and intonational distinction, appositive elements possess significant syntactic potential and stylistic impact.

When discussing their structure, it is important to emphasize that the appositive element is grammatically dependent on its main expression. This is primarily evident in the fact that the appositive element cannot be fully separated from the main part of the appositive unit. According to the well-known linguist Yu.V. Vannikov, the logical aspect of the appositive phenomenon is manifested in that two types of thinking are expressed in the sentences with appositive relations, one of which has an "additional description." The supplementary characteristic (feature) of the appositive element has been confirmed in the initial studies dedicated to the syntactic appositive phenomenon [1-180 p].

It is important to emphasize that the function of the appositive element, arising from the additional derivative, does not encompass the entire main meaning. The appositive element not only has the characteristic of providing an addition but also serves to clarify, explain, and develop the content of the main expression (sentence). All these mentioned features allow us to consider appositive constructions as a unique syntactic-stylistic phenomenon. Their use requires giving speech specific meaning and expressive-stylistic subtleties, as well as assigning significant content and emotional value to certain components of the expression [9 -115 p].

In determining the emergence of appositive relations between the components of a complex syntactic unit, the analysis of conjunctions or sentence structure is given primary importance. This approach to

identifying the existence of appositive relations between the appositive element and the main expression was first reflected in the early research on the syntax of various languages.

The appositive phenomenon is not only viewed as a unique type of syntactic relation but also as a form of balancing the distinction between hypotaxis and parataxis. For example, the linguist V.M. Milk emphasizes that conjunctions like "for" and "tough" create a balance between connection and subordination, allowing independent clauses to be incorporated within a complex syntactic unit. Instances of coordinating conjunctions fulfilling the function of subordinating conjunctions can also be observed [3-15 p]. As noted by researcher N.A. Kobrina, subordinating conjunctions such as "through," "whereas," "because," and "so that" can replace coordinating conjunctions. Conversely, coordinating conjunctions like "damit" and "denn" can be used instead of subordinating conjunctions [2-32 p].

Many linguists who have studied appositive constructions based on materials from different languages have focused on understanding the meanings of coordinating and subordinating conjunctions. For example, in Russian, conjunctions like *i*, *no*, and *da* (L.M. Loseva), in French *mais*, *et*, *or*, *ou*, *car*, *pourquoi*, *si* (I.A. Boevets and I.A. Vintman), in English *and*, *but*, *if*, *while* (G.M. Timoshenkova), and in German *und*, *aber* (M.Ya. Vays) have been analyzed in the context of appositive constructions.

It should be noted that in many cases, the appositive element, functioning as a modifier, tends to occur more frequently alongside certain conjunctions. As a result, the expression of the idea, with its specific appearance and features, forms a distinct structural manifestation of the appositive element, which is conveyed through a different element. For example: *Es war schon nachts und sie hatten etwas mehr getrunken als sonst. Auch auf den unvermuthen Sieg des Sportklubs Chemie. Auf unsere Freundschaft. Und später auf den Schornstein. Und dich.*

The analysis of the provided example shows that the conjunction *und* and *auf* used in the appositive element serve to strengthen the syntactic connection between the main expression and the appositive element. Based on the analysis of the main and secondary parts of the sentence, we have examined the use of the appositive element in German, where each of the structural components in the example acts as a separate appositive element. In this context, each element performs its own distinct role within the appositive construction.

Appositive elements, within the structure of an appositive construction, not only replicate the characteristics that are inherent to the tasks they perform but also complement and expand each other with new features. This can be observed in the analysis of these appositive elements, which are adapted to parallel combinations. Specifically, these appositive elements possess the following distinctive characteristics: first, the leading component of the appositive element, meaning the appositive element itself, is formed through a process of repetition and then expanded with the parts that follow it; the repetition of a particular sentence component is a stylistic phenomenon. Indeed, the author repeats it with the intention of refocusing the reader's attention on the depicted event or situation. The repeated component always receives logical emphasis, which, in turn, enhances its impact and significance, making the event more vivid [6 -18 p]. Thus, the stylistic functions of appositive elements, which have the characteristic of forming in this manner, are highly significant. In the following situation, we observe the phenomenon of inversion within the appositive element, as the repeated components not only repeat but also change. Therefore, a kind of synonymic situation emerges. Finally, there is the case related to the structural formation of the appositive element, which involves an economical use of language elements. As a result, we conclude that appositive elements not only serve to fill in or restore a component omitted from the main clause but can also be reconstructed with the components that follow in the main expression. This interconnection further proves the syntactic-semantic link between the main expression and the appositive element, which is a key feature of the appositive construction. The conjunctions preceding the appositive elements do not perform these functions; the syntactic connections between the appositive components can be expressed even without them. Nevertheless, we consider it appropriate to highlight the unique features of appositive elements because such elements with conjunctions play a crucial role in forming distinct

structural groups of appositive constructions. Therefore, this structural group must be specifically emphasized.

Sometimes, prepositions with the same syntactic character can participate in forming complex structural appositive constructions. For example: Er ist in der Nähe der Eldbrücke. Er kaut langsam. Welt er nachdenkt. Über Fanselow. Und über sich.

In such constructions, the resulting appositive elements are always multifunctional because the first appositive element in these cases serves two roles: it functions as an appositive for the main expression and as the main expression for the second appositive element. In a complex appositive construction, the number of appositive elements attached to the main expression can exceed two. Appositive elements with such complex structures can be observed in the following examples: Sie sah an sich herunter. Dunkles Leinenkleid. Ein wollnes Umschlantuch. Schuhe von der gewöhnlichsten Art.

Based on the analysis of certain appositive elements, it is appropriate to highlight another syntactic feature inherent to them: the structural formation of the main expression and the appositive element within the appositive construction. In short, the structural formation of the main expression does not always align with the structural formation of the appositive elements. As evidence for this conclusion, we can refer to the work of the renowned linguist T.M. Timoshenko, who, based on research using English language materials, noted the following: "Neither the main expression nor the appositive element will always have the same structural form from a communicative perspective. Therefore, an appositive construction is neither a linked compound sentence nor a subordinate compound sentence; it discovers a different structure" [5-98 p].

Indeed, if we compare the structural formation of the appositive constructions analyzed here with those that need to be analyzed, we can fully trust the validity of the above statement, because appositive constructions possess different structural formations. In such formations, either the main expression or the appositive element may have a certain degree of complexity. For example, the structural formation of the main expression in the above example sharply contrasts with the structural formation of the appositive elements in other examples. Therefore, regardless of the structural formation of the main expression relative to the appositive elements within the appositive construction, the construction itself concludes with the help of the appositive element, both structurally and semantically. Thus, the appositive element emerges as a concluding, final component in any structural formation.

Using transformational style, if we place the two appositive elements from the example above into the structure of the main expression, we would form a single subordinate clause: weil er über Fanselow und auch über sich nachdenkt. However, the writer refers to these appositive elements and uses them in the function of appositive elements to emphasize certain components of the subordinate clause, showing their importance. As a result, these appositive elements attract the reader's attention because, syntactically, appositive elements cannot stand alone; when they do appear, they must be directly related to something. This relationship occurs in both structural and semantic terms. Structural dependence is emphasized by the position of the appositive element after the main expression, i.e., it stands second in the sentence, while semantic dependence highlights that the appositive elements cannot exist without the main expression. This is because the idea omitted from the previous part of the sentence is restored, filled, and clarified by the appositive elements. Therefore, this two-way connection between the main expression and the appositive element reveals the syntactic integrity of any appositive construction, which is interpreted within the framework of a complex syntactic unit. This situation calls for the understanding that an appositive construction is a complex syntactic unit, or conversely, a complex syntactic unit is an appositive construction. For this reason, we consider it beneficial to use both of these terminological concepts in parallel throughout our work.

It should be noted that such characteristics of appositive elements can also recur within appositive constructions consisting of five or more appositive elements. For example: Die Schuhe, nun, die hatte er mitgebracht, dass waren seine. Auch die Hose. Aber den Militärrock. Einen blauen, ganz neuen. Und dann die Weste. Und den weißen Gürtel mit den Taschen.

In this example, five appositive elements are connected to the main expression within the appositive construction. Such a connection inherent to appositive elements reaffirms the points and observations mentioned earlier. This is because there exists both parallelism and sequentiality between the appositive elements and the main expression. In other words, the appositive elements are connected to the main expression they directly depend on in both parallel and sequential manners. This type of connection further enhances, supplements, and enriches the functions characteristic of appositive elements. Thus, appositive elements perform various functions within appositional constructions. Some of these functions can also be observed in the analysis of the final example: firstly, appositive elements not only form the simple structural shape of the appositional construction but also contribute to the formation of its three types of complex structures. Secondly, appositive elements possess a polyrhematic and multifunctional character. For instance, an appositive element positioned third in sequence can only attach to the main expression through the appositive element positioned second – *die hatte er mitgebracht* – as it is contextually linked to it and serves as its continuation. Similar patterns can be observed in the other appositive elements within the construction.

In appositional constructions with such complex structural forms, the syntactic links between the components are primarily restored through the lexical unit "mitbringen," which functions as a connective word. The communicative functions of the appositive elements are directed toward specifying, supplementing, clarifying, and explaining the meaning of "die" within the main expression. Therefore, numerous scientific studies dedicated to the investigation of apposition emphasize the significance, impact, and importance of the "additional" meaning conveyed by the appositive elements to the main expression [4- 344 p].

Thus, appositional constructions are a unique syntactic phenomenon that serve the function of providing additional expressions, referred to as appositive elements based on their structure. These appositive elements clarify, develop, and to some extent explain the meaning of the main expression (main clause). Such syntactic structures typically consist of two parts: the first part conveys the primary information, while the second part provides supplementary information [7 -44 p]. They unify the functional use of units in speech, through which an expression providing additional meaning emerges after the main expression, following the main idea conveyed in the discourse.

A number of Germanist scholars emphasize not only syntactic features but also stylistic characteristics when identifying the types of complex syntactic structures. One such scholar is B.T. Tursunov, who, based on German language materials, studies the phenomenon of apposition as a distinct type of syntactic connection. He highlights the importance of considering both syntactic and stylistic features when determining the structural types of complex syntactic units. [8 -44 p]. B.T. Tursunov identifies the following structural types of appositive elements: appositive elements with a connector, appositive elements without a connector, appositive elements based on lexical repetition, appositive elements located at a certain distance, appositive elements used as response replicas, and complex-structured appositive elements.

It should be noted that both connector-based and connectorless as well as other structural constructions manifest as an integral part of any complex syntactic whole, and they can be considered as variations of complex syntactic structure.

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